

CORPORATE PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF EFFECTIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

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Annotations: This article reveals the urgent tasks of modern Uzbekistan at a new stage of development, on the threshold of the Third Renaissance, as the basis of social reforms aimed at increasing the efficiency of education, improving the system of competitive training, creating a social environment that values Enlightenment.

Key words: management, university management, corporate pedagogical, management methods, corporate governance, independence in management.

The effort of each Higher Educational Institution to establish a particular model based on its features is becoming one of the most pressing jobs, based on the general principles of the global approach of corporate governance. The major connection in personnel training as part of these changes is also the improvement of the Higher Education system, modernization, and the creation of a quality system with a constructive use of developed countries' experience. "For our country, we must clearly establish the priority directions in the sphere of research," he says. No state can develop all fields of science in some way.

As a result, we are also dedicated to the creation of multi-priority scientific directions each year" [1]. Of course, professional education and the organization of effective ongoing education are essential for the accomplishment of these priority duties. The creation of a training structure for potential and competitive personnel through updates and structural changes in higher education has also become a social imperative. "Higher education institutions are gradually given academic and financial independence" [1] for this goal. It is also critical to

implement management reforms in the higher education system, to renounce management principles of bureaucracy and centralization, and to establish open, transparent, and participatory management prints.

In general, one of the main goals is to improve the effectiveness of management in Uzbekistan's higher education system by introducing new management principles, bringing management experience from advanced foreign higher education institutions, and increasing the effectiveness of education through this.

Indeed, the history of industrialized countries demonstrates that social growth is dependent on a professionally constructed system of education, on its efficacy, and on the evolution of education reforms. In our country, too, education reform, assuring the coherence and systematization of the system of continuous education, and strengthening education administration are being seen as a way of insuring a new attrition quickly.

In recent years, reforms have been implemented in our country's educational system; nonetheless, while many opportunities have been created, many challenges remain. The fact that the head of state places special emphasis on education, with the president himself at the front of these reforms, demonstrates how many educational reforms are being implemented for the benefit of society. "When we handle science and education correctly," our president says, "competent specialists in all disciplines create themselves." Furthermore, at a meeting of the president and leaders of science held on May 24, 2019, at the National University of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev highlighted that the only way to reform education and scientific progress. After all, "I propose to name 2020 the year of development of Science, Enlightenment, and Digital Economy" [1] in order to further develop science in our country, educate our youth as owners of deep knowledge, high spirituality, and culture, and to intensify the work that has begun on the formation of a competitive economy and to raise it to a new,

modern level. It is worth noting that "the adoption of continuous education in our republic necessitates the resolution of a number of tasks and the continual improvement and development of educational authority." It is critical to offer quality normative-legal documents to the educational process on time. Legislative and normative papers on the application of the aforementioned laws were re-adopted in the following areas over the past period:

- Management of education and training system;
- Content reform of the educational process;
- Financing and material and technical support;
- Retraining and professional development of pedagogical and scientific-pedagogical personnel;
- Development of education services market;
- International relations in the field of education and training;
- Learning foreign languages;
- Create electronic libraries and consolidate into a single network;
- Provision of social and financial public assistance in the field of education, etc."[2].

Accelerating the process of coordination and acceptance of international standards, as well as compliance with current systems, has been shown to boost the attractiveness of Uzbekistan's educational system. To strengthen higher education administration and systematically expand the share of scientific professors in higher education, the procedure for self-determination and issuance of scientific degrees to higher educational institutions was established in 2021. "In the coming year, 30 of our country's finest institutions will be able to design instructional programs, get quotas, and autonomously address financial concerns." Scientific titles of associate professors and professors, as well as the right to issue scientific degrees of doctor of philosophy and science, will be handed to scientific councils of famous institutions in their direction"[3]. This is also a crucial step in modernizing Higher Education Administration. Indeed,

giving him freedom and financial independence will be vital for the creation of corporate governance in higher education.

It is also required to improve the efficiency of higher education institutions, raise the indicators of competitive people training, reform management, liberalize higher education management, and modify the way management performance is measured. Employees in management who are surrounded by bureaucratic interactions, meetings, and organizational concerns "attempt to lose a strong, educated scientist while working." A few "treatises" with 32 pages, the printing of manuals for two years, and almost no writing will be included in the authorship of five teachers 25-30 years old. In a year, recruited young dummies do not produce a single thesis. What type of science and scientific competency can be discussed?" [4]. As a result, it is crucial to encourage and support personnel of a higher educational institution's administration, as well as new professors and teachers, and, most significantly, to free them from financial reliance.

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